

SYNTHESIS OF METAL AND METAL OXIDE/CNTs HYBRID NANOPARTICLES AND THEIR REINFORCEMENTS IN POLYMERS

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Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are one of the ideal materials to hybridize with various metal and metal oxide nanoparticles to design nanoarchitectures that are extremely attractive as supports for heterogeneous catalysts, and multifunctional polymer composite for structural applications. Many studies on CNTs/polymer composites have revealed that good dispersion and strong interfacial bonding between CNTs and the polymer matrix result in strong reinforcement of the polymers. In the current study, we have explored the synthesis of metal and metal oxides such as silver (Ag), gold (Au), copper (Cu), diamond, Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) and Zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles coated CNTs using microwave and sonochemical methods. Pristine CNTs were synthesized using first nano-300 CVD technique and iron based metal catalyst. The as-prepared hybrid nanoparticles were further infused into the nylon-6 or epoxy resin system using melt extrusion process or non-contact mixing process to produce hybrid nanoparticles based polymer nanocomposites for multifunctional applications

1 Introduction

Composite materials are engineered materials made from two or more constituent materials with significantly different physical or chemical properties which remain separate and distinct within the finished structure [1]. The matrix and reinforcement constitute the composite. The matrix material surrounds and supports the reinforcement materials by preserving their relative positions. The reinforcements impart special physical

(mechanical, thermal and optical) properties to enhance the matrix properties. With our continuing quest for lighter and stronger composites, the demand for new types of materials is increasing. No longer are the traditional composite materials capable of satisfying our stringent requirements, nor can they be engineered to control properties at the atomic or molecular level. The essence of such control in properties has derived from the fact that the aggregate properties of materials under external excitations such as force, pressure or temperature, are largely dictated by their molecular level orientation. Eventually, material which allows working at the molecular level will be highly competent to be engineered according to specific requirements [2].

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) since their discovery [3] become an important scientific field for the extensive research due to their interesting physics properties and technological applications [4]. They are excellent multifunctional materials in terms of mechanical strength, thermal, and electrical conductivities. These multifunctional properties, as well as the small size of the structures, make CNTs ideal building blocks in developing nanocomposites. The unique properties of CNTs such as ultra high electrical conductivity and ultra-high mechanical strength result directly from the macroscopic understanding of molecular carbon's unique properties such as ballistic transport and exceedingly high mechanical strength. Researchers have envisaged taking advantage of their conductivity and high aspect ratio to produce conductive plastics with exceedingly

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low percolation thresholds. The ultimate mechanical filler material is carbon nanotubes. Nanotubes can have diameters ranging from 1 to 100 nm and lengths of up to millimeters [5]. Their densities can be as low as 1.3 g/cm³ and their Young's moduli are superior to all carbon fibers with values greater than 1 TPa [6]. However, their strength is what really sets them apart. The highest measured strength for carbon nanotube was 63 GPa [7].

Recently, there has been great interest in the metal coating of CNTs [8] for creating new metal-matrix-based carbon tube composites. The metallization process is a kind of surface modification of CNTs. This kind of modification not only can increase the surface active sites to improve bonding between nanotube and resin or ceramic [9], but also can preserve the superior performance and excellent intrinsic properties of CNTs in the composites. Furthermore, this metal coating of CNTs has been shown to have significant potential for the fabrication of new powder CNTs-metal composites [10] thus extending the application fields of CNTs. In the past, some successful attempts have been made to synthesize nanoparticles of copper and copper oxides, using various method including sonochemical, microwave irradiation photochemical, hydrothermal, solvothermal, electrochemical, sol-gel methods, solid-state reactions, chemical reduction and decomposition route and so on [11].

Microwaves are a portion of the electromagnetic spectrum with frequencies in the range of 300 MHz to 300 GHz. The degree of interaction of microwaves with a dielectric medium is related to the material's dielectric constant and dielectric loss. [12] When microwaves penetrate and propagate through a dielectric solution or suspension, the internal electric fields generated within the affected volume induce translation motions of free or bound charges such as electrons or ions and rotate charged complexes such as dipoles [12]. The resistance of these induced motions due to inertial, elastic, and frictional force, which are frequency dependent, causes losses and attenuates the electric field. The main advantages of microwave-assisted reactions

over conventional methods in synthesis are: (a) the kinetics of the reaction are increased by one to two orders of magnitude, (b) novel phases are formed, (c) the initial heating is rapid, which can lead to energy savings, and (d) selective formation of one phase over another often occurs. [13] One possible hypothesis for these microwave-induced effects are the generation of localized high temperatures at the reaction sites to enhance reaction rates in an analogous manner to that of ultrasonic waves, where both high temperatures and pressures have been reported during reaction. The enhanced kinetics of crystallization can lead to energy savings of up to 90% [14].

The polyol method is a low-temperature process that is environmentally friendly because the reactions are carried out under closed-system conditions. It was first introduced to produce metal submicron-sized powders. In this method, a suitable solid metal salt is suspended in a liquid polyol. The suspension is stirred and heated to a certain temperature; the reduction of the starting compound yields fine metal powders. The polyol itself acts not only as a solvent in the process but also as a stabilizer, limiting particle growth and restricting agglomeration. Recently, this method has also been extended to the preparation of metal oxides and metal chalcogenides. [15]. We have recently shown to synthesize the Ag/CNTs hybrid nanoparticle using sonochemical method [16-17]. This sonochemical processing is a useful technique for generating novel materials with unusual properties. Sonochemistry arises from the acoustic cavitations phenomenon, that is, the formation, growth and implosive collapse of bubbles in a liquid medium [18]. The extremely high temperatures (>5000 K) and pressure (>20 MPa) and high cooling rates (>10⁷ K s⁻¹) [19] attained during acoustic cavitations lead to many unique properties in the irradiated solution.

In the present research we have synthesized the metal or metal oxide coated CNTs hybrid nanoparticles using sonochemical or microwave irradiation technique and these hybrid nanoparticles were further reinforced

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into polymer such as Nylon-6 and tested for their mechanical properties.

2 Experimental Method

Ag or Cu coated CNTS composites were prepared by microwave heating of ethylene glycol (EG, Aldrich) solutions of silver (II) acetate or copper (II) acetate (Aldrich) precursor salts. 250 gm silver or copper(II)acetate dissolved in 100 ml of ethylene glycol in a round bottom flask by using magnetic stirrer and 500mg of Cetyl Trimethyl Ammonium Bromide (CTAB) is used as a surfactant. All solutions were prepared using reagent grade chemicals. Then 50 mg CNTs were dispersed in the solution. The flask was placed in the center of a microwave oven (SHARP 1000V/R21HT) and irradiated for 10 min under microwave power of 60 W. After the reaction completed, the solution was cooled to room temperature, and the products obtained were separated from the liquid by centrifugation and followed by repeated washing with absolute ethanol several times and vacuum dried at room temperature overnight.

TiO₂ coated CNTs hybrid nanoparticles were synthesized using a titanium (IV) tetraisopropoxide (TIOP) as a reducing agent in the presence of Ethanol and water solvent to obtain titanium dioxide nanoparticles. 100 mg of CNTs were magnetically stirred with 80 ml of ethanol and 60 ml of water in 150 ml capacity glass flask for 30 min in a to uniformly disperse the CNTs in the solution. 200 mg of Cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) is used as a surfactant and protecting agent in the solution and stirred for 10 more min. 0.8 ml of TIOP was then added and stirred for another 5 min before carrying out the Sonochemical reaction. The magnetically stirred solution of metal salts, solvent, surfactant and CNTs is then sonochemically irradiated for 3 hours at 55% amplitude at room temperature. The reaction product was separated using a centrifuge and repeated washing with water and finally ethanol. The final product was dried under vacuum at room temperature for overnight. These hybrid nanoparticles were further calcined at 400°C for

2 hrs to produce crystalline TiO₂ nanoparticle on CNTs.

2.1 Fabrication of TiO₂/CNTs and Synthesized TiO₂ Infused Nylon-6 Filaments

TiO₂/CNTs hybrid nanoparticles and neat Nylon-6 powders were carefully measured in the ratio of 1:99 by weight and were dry mixed using Thinky mixing to produce a uniform mixture of nanoparticles and neat Nylon-6 powder. The mixture was then dried in a dryer for 16 hrs and extruded as a single filament using a *Wayne Yellow Label Table Top Extruder*. Before carrying out the extrusion, the die chamber was flushed out with neat Nylon-6 powder to remove the contamination. Thermostatically controlled five heating zones were used to melt the mixture before extrusion, three inside the barrel and two in the die zone at set temperatures of 226°C, 235°C, 243°C, 246.1°C and 246.1°C respectively. The composite filaments with constant tension were extruded at a screw speed of 8 rpm and feed rate of approximately 80 g/h. Then the filaments were stabilized by using a setup of two godet machines and a heater and the filaments were finally wound on a spool using *Wayne Desktop Filament Winder* at a winding speed of 45 rpm. These filaments were kept in a vacuum desiccator for overnight to remove the remaining moisture present in the filaments. The filaments were then characterized for their fiber diameter using SEM and tensile tests using materials testing equipment.

The XRD measurements were carried out using a Rigaku, D/Max 2200 instrument. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) examinations of the samples were carried out with a JEOL-2010 microscope. The powdered samples were dispersed in ethanol and subjected to ultrasonic treatment and dropped on to a conventional carbon coated molybdenum grid.

3 Results and discussion

Figure 1 shows the powder XRD patterns of (a) CNTs, b) Ag/CNTs c) Cu/CNTs nanoparticles. Figure 1 indicates that the CNTs, Ag/CNTs and Cu/CNTs composite particles are crystalline and all the peaks match with the standard

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Figure 1. The powder XRD patterns of (a) CNTs, b)Ag/CNTs, c) Cu/CNTs nanoparticles

JCPDS file numbers of CNTs (26-1077), Cu (4-0836) and , Ag (04-0783). As shown in Figure 2 (a) depicts the X-ray diffraction of as prepared CNTs and all the peaks match with JCPDF # 26-1077 of crystalline graphite. The figure 2(c) CNTs/TiO₂ nanoparticles were highly crystalline in nature and was found to be of anatase phase of TiO₂. All the diffraction peaks match very well with anatase-syn TiO₂ of JCPDF # 21-1272. The CNTs X-ray diffraction peaks are not clearly distinguishable because of the close proximity of TiO₂ peaks and these peaks may be overshadowed by high intensity peaks of TiO₂ peaks.

Figure 2. The powder XRD patterns of (a) CNTs, b)TiO₂, c) CNTs/TiO₂ nanoparticles

Figure 3 shows the transmission electron micrograph (TEM) of a) as prepared carbon nanotubes (CNTs), b) CNTs coated with silver, c) TiO₂ and d) Cu coated nanoparticles respectively. TEM studies were carried out to understand the CNTs structure and extent of Ag, TiO₂ and Cu coating on CNTs. TEM micrographs in Figure 3(b) depicts the Ag nanoparticles coated on CNTs and the particles sizes measure are about ~5-10 nm. Figure 3(c) shows the TiO₂ nanoparticles coated on CNTs and these particles sizes measure are ~ 5 nm. The Figure 3(d) shows the Cu coated CNTs and these coated copper particle are about 1-5 nm in sizes. These particles were coated entire volume of the CNTs.

Figure 3. TEM micrographs of a) CNTs, b) silver coated CNTs, c) TiO₂ coated CNTs and Cu coated CNTs.

Figure 4 shows the experimental results for the ultimate tensile strength and elongation (%) for the neat a) Nylon-6, b) 1% TiO₂ infused Nylon-6 c) 1% CNTs infused Nylon-6, and d) 1% TiO₂ coated CNTs infused Nylon-6 composite fibers. These results show that the behavior of 1% TiO₂/CNTs Nylon-6 composite fibers fall in-between the 1wt% CNTs and 1wt% of TiO₂ infusion in Nylon-6. The failure stress of the extruded Nylon-6 fibers infused with 1% TiO₂/CNTs nanoparticles is ~ 37.16% higher than the neat extruded Nylon-6 fiber and the improvement in the tensile modulus is 548.8%.

Though the TiO₂/CNTs nanoparticles have exhibited better interfacial bonding strength the

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tensile strength are little (~10MPa) lower than the 1wt% CNTs infused Nylon-6 fibers. This can be related to the large particle size and the tendency of the nanoparticles to agglomerate and form bundles around the CNTs surfaces.

Figure 4 Tensile response of (a) Neat Nylon-6 (b) TiO₂-Nylon-6 (c) CNTs-Nylon-6 (d) TiO₂/CNTs-Nylon-6

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